

Remembering David Kunzle

by Ian Gordon

<https://ijoca.blogspot.com/2024/01/ian-gordon-remembers-david-kunzle.html>

David Kunzle (April 17, 1936 – January 1, 2024)

Vale David Kunzle. I received the news that David had died from Roger Sabin when I was in London in early January 2024. As it happened, I was at Cambridge, his undergraduate university, the day before I heard, and on my return to London walked past his doctoral home at the Courtauld Institute of Art.

David was a formative influence on my work. Like many comics fans at the time, I first encountered David through his 1974 introduction to and translation of Ariel Dorfman and Armand Mattelart's *How to Read Donald Duck*. The red-hot prose of that work is best understood as a visceral reaction to the vicious Pinochet regime and the comics analyzed had been altered by the Chilean publishers who were not sympathetic to the Allende socialist government. But my engagement with David's work only came later.

In 1989 I decided to do my doctoral dissertation on comic strips. In that same year the University of California Press announced the forthcoming publication of the second volume of his *The History of the Comic Strip*. At \$110 it was beyond my graduate student budget, so I sought a review copy. Michael Kazin then the Reviews Editor at *Tikkun*, who I had met at the Smithsonian, said no, but suggested the *American Quarterly*. At first Charles Bassett, then the book review editor, said no but after he received a volume from the University Press of Mississippi, Joseph (Rusty) Witek's *Comic Books as History: The Narrative Art of Jack Jackson, Art Spiegelman, and Harvey Pekar*, he said yes provided I did a combined review.

Somewhat miffed that this fellow Witek had used a version of the title I wanted for my dissertation I said yes. In preparation while waiting for Volume 2, which only came out in mid 1990, I studied Volume 1 closely after previously only having given it a cursory read. I remember this well because I was traveling home to Australia and borrowed a copy from the University of Sydney library and read about a third, lugging it between Sydney and Melbourne and back again. Returning to the USA I spent a week or so in Los Angeles at my grad school friend Charles Shindo's family home and he borrowed a copy from his alma mater, USC, and I may have even read some of it on the beach. Finally, back in Washington, DC I finished Volume 1 at the Library of Congress and moved to Volume 2 that I had by then received. The review duly appeared in *American Quarterly*.^[1] After completing the review essay I began the research for my dissertation. In many ways my approach to studying comics was shaped through this review essay. I wanted to use Kunzle's methods to study American comics and was too sharp with Rusty's work for not doing quite what I wanted it to do. Stressing the merits of Kunzle I neglected the merits of Witek, something that I later addressed.^[2]

Of Kunzle's work I had this to say in the *American Quarterly*:

Kunzle's first volume *History of the Comic Strip: Vol. 1, The Early Comic Strip*, published in 1973, contained an account of the crucial transformation in graphic narrative in late eighteenth-century England; "the stylistic revolution in popular graphic art known as caricature" (Kunzle, Berkeley, 1973, 1). Kunzle demonstrated that before

Hogarth introduced a comic element in graphic narrative during the eighteenth century, it was primarily concerned with religious, moral, and political themes of a didactic or propagandistic nature. The narrative in Hogarth's panels was also easier to follow than in earlier, more static, graphic narrative. But Hogarth was no caricaturist. Nor did he use speech balloons, contrary to the view held by many comic art historians.' Caricature, a method of capturing a person's essential character by the exaggeration of features in a loose line drawing, entered the public realm of European art late in the eighteenth century. It lent itself to political commentary and to a new style of narrative fiction: the comic strip. Rodolphe Topffer (1799-1846) undertook the first sustained work in the new medium of the comic strip, and *History of the Comic Strip: Vol. 2, The Nineteenth Century* opens with a discussion of his work.

Kunzie argues that Topffer and those who followed him, most notably Cham (Charles-Henri-Amedee de Noe), Leonce Petit, Adolphe Willette, and Wilhelm Busch, effected a profound change in graphic narrative. They produced comic strips that aimed to entertain. The works presented not the facile comic strip offerings one so often encounters in the late twentieth century, but extended tales, gathered in albums, that addressed the emerging bourgeois order of Europe. For instance, between 1830 and 1846, Topffer lampooned the pretensions of the petite bourgeoisie on the make, parodied scientific research, and in his final work, derided would-be revolutionists. To tell these stories, Topffer and the others developed new graphic narrative techniques. These included dried pen etching and stunning montage sequences in which the images cut back and forth between protagonists or ranged over movement through time and space. Kunzle's detailed account of the European development of the comic strip is relevant to an American Studies audience because despite the unique and "specifically American humorous tradition" displayed in early American comic strips (5), their form, and indeed their content, owed much to the earlier European work. (242-243).

And "David Kunzle's *History* sets a standard for discussion and analysis of the comic art form. He not only recounts the technical and stylistic development of the form but sets it within the cultural matrix of nineteenth century Europe." (246)

For good measure I should note that I saw Rusty's work positing something that indeed happened and he was ahead of the curve in seeing that possibility and explaining the way it took shape, "Witek's book raises the possibility that comic books may transcend their formulaic nature and produce a new literary medium." (246)

Having finished his second volume David seemed to balk at doing the third volume that he had originally intended. In May 1992 he wrote to the art historian Rebecca Zurier had received a Swann Foundation fellowship for her work on the Ashcan School. He proposed a collaboration on a third volume that would run from 1896 to Krazy Kat stopping short of the adventure strips of the 1930s. Given her path to tenure as an art historian had been mapped out for her in discussions with her Department Zurier could not take up Kunzle's offer, and she directed him to me. In 1992 just as I was wrapping up my dissertation, I received a letter from Kunzle (*see below*). Busy with meeting the demand from the graduate Dean of my university that all 200 figures appear in portrait form with full captions, rather than a mix of portrait and landscape, and then with defending the dissertation I did not reply until October. To say I was flattered was an understatement. I was flabbergasted that Kunzle had contacted me and proposed such a collaboration. I of course said yes. So where is that third volume? I said yes conditionally since I wanted to get some publications out before turning to that collaboration. I also hoped

to stay in America and was able to do so through some employment at the Smithsonian allowed as gaining work experience under my F1 visa. David replied and we agreed to meet in Los Angeles in 1993 to discuss the volume. I sent him my dissertation.

In 1993 he graciously collected me at the LA train station, and we and his wife Marjoyre had dinner at their UCLA house. I remember the dinner because at one point David excused himself and returned with a rapier and told me about his performance with an Elizabethan troupe. I was unsure if I should engage him with the fork I was using to eat pasta. I am not sure if it was that evening, or perhaps in a letter that I no longer have, that David responded to my dissertation with the comment “was it as bad as that” meaning the mass commodification of comic art in the American comic strip. I now wonder if perhaps he was also asking me to think a little more about comic art that had not been so drastically commodified and perhaps expand my vision from the very real role comics played in shaping consumer culture.

By this stage though I had decided to return to Australia since long term work was not presenting itself in America. I am not sure exactly what David, and I decided on the proposed collaboration, or indeed if we decided anything. Perhaps it disappeared as other priorities and the passage of time took us further away from the project. From a letter from Martin Barker sometime in mid to late 1993 I do know that David had been speaking with him to about the project. But as Martin suggested I think David was not as engaged with Volume 3 as he had other work he wanted to do.

In the last ten years or so other scholars have filled some of the gaps left by the absence of a third volume. Beyond my own initial attempts to place comics in a broader development of twentieth century American culture Christina Meyer’s *Producing Mass Entertainment*, Lara Saguisag’s *Incorrigibles and Innocents*, and Alex Beringer’s *Lost Literacies* are all invaluable works that should be read in the absence of that volume. One can hope for many more works like these to plug the gaps.

Many non-academic readers with an interest in understanding the history of comics have appreciated Kunzle’s work. But that was not always the case. For instance, when I visited Bill Blackbeard in 1991, he dismissed David’s work as simply reproducing every early image he could find and not worth attention. His influence on others was perhaps pernicious since Bob Beerbohm, very much a fan of the work in his latter years, told me he had been put off by Blackbeard’s comments. I can only surmise that Blackbeard’s view was colored by a desire to claim comic strips as a uniquely American form and David’s work demonstrating long antecedents of commercial graphic work (and not fanciful connections like hieroglyphics) upset that apple cart. On the scholarly front David was aware of Donald Ault and I do wonder if they discussed Disney.

David Kunzle encouraged my work especially in the early years when I was trying to make a career. Other scholars like the Australian historian Richard Scully and the British historian Patrick Hagopian, to whom David sent photo documentation of his anti-Vietnam war posters, have mentioned David’s kindness. I was very happy to meet David again in 2017 at a conference in the UK. By then he had returned to the study of comics at a time when many more scholars had turned their attention to both comics and David’s work. The following year at the International Graphic Novels and Comics conference in Bournemouth I was able to thank him publicly, during my keynote address, for his help, encouragement, and exemplary scholarship. His gracious nod in thanks was as wonderful as the first letter I received from him. We have lost a scholar of enormous importance.

[1] Ian Gordon, "'But Seriously, Folks ...': - Comic Art and History," *American Quarterly*, 43 (June 1991): 122-126. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18359576>

[2] Ian Gordon, "In Praise of Comic Books as History: Joseph Witek and Comics Scholarship," in *Graphic Subjects: Critical Essays on Autobiography and the Graphic Novel*, Michael Chaney ed., (Madison: University of Wisconsin Press, 2011): 244-246. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18408332>

David Kunzle to Rebecca Zurier, May 8, 1992:

UNIVERSITY OF CALIFORNIA, LOS ANGELES

BERKELEY • DAVIS • IRVINE • LOS ANGELES • RIVERSIDE • SAN DIEGO • SAN FRANCISCO

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DEPARTMENT OF ART HISTORY
405 HILGARD AVENUE
LOS ANGELES, CALIFORNIA 90024-1417
(213) 206-0905

May 8 1992

Rebecca Zurier
Dept of History of Art
U of Michigan
Ann Arbor Mi 48109

Dear Rebecca

I have been thinking about you and the nice long ms letter you wrote some time ago (it was undated - ah I checked the envelope, Jan 23) a lot.

As I complete what I hope is the final major revision on my Nicaraguan Revolutionary Murals book, and return to my mainline Dutch 17th century work; with my final say on the Disney comics (basically the English version of the little German book I sent you, due out in an anthology to be edited by Eric Smoodin, except I haven't heard from him in months); I have to face the prospects of the Third Comic Strip Volume you are so touchingly concerned about.

I recently had my 56th birthday; I have a few books (at least two) on Dutch 17th c. soldiering in art, possibly one on women, then who knows peasants (all Dutch 17thc.) This will take me into a ripe old age. However, I do agree there is room for this third Comic Strip volume, so I begin to wonder, alive to your own expertise and interest, whether we shouldn't collaborate on it.

For ^{years} ~~a~~ while I thought I could get graduate students here going on this; not a sign. Maybe you could do better. Either as research assistants, or as contributors of a chapter on each major strip/phenomenon. The period I am thinking of would run from 1896 to Crazy Kat (~~short of?~~), short of the adventure strips of the 1930s, probably.

But International (Europe included): You would be wholly in charge of the American, the bigger and more important side; I would slog away, in between Dutch 17th art, at the European. I am always in Europe anyway. You know American history so much better than I do. I could help you on your way a bit with files of comic strips culled from Puck, Judge and Life. I forgot to say that this volume, as I announced in my preface to Vol II, would have to include the magazine strip in the U.S. from its beginnings (mid 19th c?); apart from the three major magazines mentioned, there are I guess many others, such as Schnedderedengg, just ~~to~~ mentioned one exoticum (it is out of New York but in German, and I got to it because of its massive Busch plagiaries)

Which would make the title awkward: Maybe "Comic Strip in America from the beginnings ~~to 1930~~ (or whenever one can determine it started), mid 19th c.?) to 193X; with a subtitle.

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say with a chapter (or two or three) on the European strip 1896- 193X or whatever cutoff point suggests itself there.

I don't know whether I would even need to have general editorial control over the whole, or share it equally with you (this sounds about right), or ~~let~~ let you have it entirely to yourself (over the U.S. part at any rate). I think we can agree on broad political lines: no student (if students are indeed drafting chapters) would be allowed to deny the existence of imperialism, or the alienating effects of capitalism!

Something to think on. Do please let me know how this might fit in with your future research plans, assuming you are now sufficiently unpacked to look to the future at all.

I don't know Paul Jerome Croce, the Disneyan. There was a conference on Disney recently - or was it just a panel of Disney at some Am. Stud. Conf, at which I had the peculiar distinction of having (so Donald says and did) my work on the Barks comics read in my absence. (Q.: do I put that on my Vita?). Could that have been the same one you refer to at New Orleans?

Lovely to hear you say MoMA sold stacks of my book; you exaggerate, of course, but fact is I have never seen the book on public display anywhere!

No idea whether Art Journal ran my letter.

Wally

KUNZLE

PS And your particular interest in domestic themes would fruit in the 20th c. American comic, right?

Rebecca Zurier to David Kunzle, June 13, 1992:

DEPARTMENT OF THE HISTORY OF ART
THE UNIVERSITY OF MICHIGAN
ANN ARBOR, MICHIGAN 48109-1357

TAPPAN HALL
(313) 764-5400

13 June 1992

David Kunzle
Department of Art History
University of California, Los Angeles
405 Hilgard Ave.
Los Angeles, CA 90024-1417

Dear David,

How nice to hear from you. The enclosed reminded me of you recently, on the plane from Prague back to New York. Tom and I used up frequent flyer miles in Europe; Czechoslovakia a fascinating place, just a week before the election. Plenty of political graphics to be seen, much sharper, sometimes darker than American campaign posters. And much different from Italian campaign posters which tend to show politicians beaming away as in high school yearbook photos. Have you ever visited Prague? Do, before it changes for the worse.

I'm honored that you'd think about sharing the next comics volume with me but I can say pretty definitely no thank you. First of all, I've spent this semester discussing the tenure track with deans and department members and we've finally arrived at a plan that will keep me pretty busy for the next few years. And there are a few projects beyond that, pretty sketchy now but that could take me in different directions from the comics. But also, I don't think I could match your scholarship. I don't know American history that well, I don't have the kind of overview that you do, and I don't think I have it in me to be as thorough as you are.

But I have a suggestion: write to Ian Gordon c/o Fellows' Office, National Museum of American History, Smithsonian Institution, Washington, DC 20560. As I may have mentioned, Ian reviewed your book in American Quarterly. He's Australian, came to the States for graduate school in American history at the University of Rochester, is finishing a dissertation on comics and mass culture from the nineteenth to the early twentieth century—he's interested in how the comics began as a local, urban phenomenon and became national, and in doing so paved the way for national advertising. Maybe he'd send you some chapters to read. I think you'd enjoy working with him because you'd both share an outsider's view of American culture, but since he's not an art historian he brings different questions to bear and could learn from you. I don't know how much he gets into close analysis of narrative, which you do so well. I have no idea what his plans are for the next few years—he may not know, either. But perhaps you could interest him in sharing the project with a few others.

When you write to Ian, you might offer to drive out to Costa Mesa to meet with him during the American Studies Association conference, November 5-8, at which he'll be giving a paper in a session on "reading the popular and popular reading." That way, I'd get to see you too. Oddly enough, both Ian

—Alas
I'm
in Europe

and I will be going out to that same godforsaken part of California (Anaheim this time) again in April to participate in a session on Urban Visuality at the annual meeting of the Organization of American Historians. Why couldn't either of these organizations have chosen to meet closer to the water?

Speaking of conferences, Tom gave a paper at that narrative conference in Nashville (I couldn't go) and hoped to run into you. He found it very lively, perhaps because there were almost no art historians there (the program included everything from law to Freud's Wolfman to Twin Peaks to Renato Rosaldo raking Norman Bryson over the coals). As far as I know, Paul Croce didn't participate but Joseph Witek, who is a colleague of his, gave a paper in the session on Disney. Too bad you had to miss it.

I'm sorry that I can't respond differently but hope that you'll find a way to stick with the comics project. Do keep me informed. And thanks so much for writing.

Yours,

Rebecca

Kunzle to Gordon, July 1, 1992:

Gordon to Kunzle, October 1, 1992:

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October 1, 1992.

David Kunzle
Visiting Fellow
Clare Hall
Cambridge, ENGLAND
CB3 9AL

Dear David Kunzle,

Thank you for the letter of July 1. I am flattered that you wish me to consider collaborating with you on the third volume of the History of the Comic Strip. I understand that we will need to discuss the matter before agreeing to undertake the project together, but my answer is yes.

Enclosed is a copy of the introduction to my dissertation. It should give you some sense of the compatibility of our work. If you want to read the whole thing before you come back to the U.S. I'll send a copy -- it's 550 pages including figures (263 pages of text). I think my approach to comics is close enough to yours that we should be able to work together. I agree with the general approach for the proposed work you outlined in your May 8 letter to Rebecca. I would want to add a chapter or segment on Australia.

At the risk of seeming a careerist I should point out my priorities over the next few years. At almost 38 (I began my undergraduate education at 28), and just completed my doctorate, I need to find a tenure track job. For the moment I want to work in the U.S. I need to get some publications under my belt. To this end I am currently working with Garth Jowett (he's in Communications at Houston) on an anthology of critical essays on American comics, which is under consideration by Sage. I also want to work on my dissertation for publication as a work in its own right. My ideal publisher would be the University of California Press. I would appreciate your advise on how to approach them. Do you have a contract with them for the third volume of the History?

Apart from the career opportunities it may present I am eager to work on the third volume of the History. Having lectured others on their foolishness in overlooking the contribution the first two volumes make to an understanding of twentieth-century American comics I feel compelled to do what I can to ensure that the third volume, which should make these connections obvious even to dolts like Maurice Horn, appears.

I will be in California at the Organization of American Historians meeting April 15-18 next year. Perhaps we can get together then.

Regards,

Ian Gordon
NMAH, Rm 1040, MRC 605
Smithsonian Institution
Washington, D.C. 20560.

Kunzle to Gordon, November 11, 1992:

TMI
Dec 30

DAVID & MARJOYRE KUNZLE
VISITING FELLOW
CLARE HALL
HERSCHEL ROAD
CAMBRIDGE
CB3 9AL

November 11 1992

Dear Ian Gordon -

I was glad to get your encouraging response here. Since I wrote to Rebecca I have ^{been} haunted by the boastful and vain -glorious list of books I ~~wrote~~ gave in my letter as needing to be written before I get back to Comic Strip History III -- boasting with death in a draft obituary. I'll be happy to get the one on Dutch 17th c. art done in the next few years, the rate I'm going.

So - it sounds like you should not give my proposal priority, given your other career needs. This suits me fine, since I'm not anxious to be thinking about it much in the next couple of years or so. But it would be nice to have something simmering away on the back burner, that would turn into Vol III, eventually. Sounds like the Gordon-Jowett anthology is the first in line, and then your Diss. I suspect UC Press would ~~want~~ to know from me, if they considered your Diss., how it would relate to my promised volume, for which I should stress I do NOT have a contract, just a broad understanding. I have not said anything over the last years which would encourage them to think I was gung-ho on it anyway. Maybe your diss. belongs in a Communications series?

Anyway, I would love to look at the whole text, perhaps you could bring it with you when you come to CA for the Org. American Historians - to be held exactly where? I am around at that time, though teaching again, so LA would be more convenient

I think your idea linking comics and advertising is primordial. Maybe it is just that commercial spin-off that depresses me.

So let's take a long view. Who knows, maybe a graduate student will turn up at UCLA who would want to help. Perhaps I should start giving seminars in the comic strip, which I have done so sparingly in the past. But David

April
15-18

University of the
West of England

St Matthias Campus
Oldbury Court Road, Fishponds
Bristol BS16 2JP

Telephone 0272 655384 ext 4333

Facsimile

Dear Ian,

I suspect you must by now have a pretty low opinion of me. It's three months since you went to all the trouble and cost of copying your PhD to me — and you've neither had an acknowledgment, nor a comment, not even a reply to your very specific query. And for all those, a very genuine apology. Truth is, your thesis has been sitting in a very public place in my office, daily accusing me, but I haven't dared to sit down and begin on it, because of the most horrible fear of my teaching life. I have now begun to emerge from that, and I have finally sat down and indulged myself in what has turned out to be the total pleasure and fascination — and that is something I often get to say about PhD Theses — of your work.

Ian, it's excellent, and I say it though I'm sure you already know it. It's a genuine contribution to our understanding of the comic tradition/history, and its imbrication with American social/cultural life. Speaking pure personally, I was most fascinated by your discussions of DC/Superman and the Island

World War. That really does invite a researcher now to get into DC's archives, as people have with Disney for example, to examine the institutional processes that led to the paradoxical situation that the most popular, and the most officially-sanctioned of the war-time comic books, was the one who involved himself least in "war activities" and most in "summer activities." (Your argument, incidentally, serendipitously Umberto Eco's very forthright analysis of Superman in his The Role of The Reader.)

So, just question - when, and in what form, is all this being published? It must be - it's far too important to be idle. If a book isn't on immediately, have you thought about a series of journal articles?

Now, briefly to other matters. I'm probably far too late, and you'll probably spit feathers at the mention, but if you still want me to do an introduction to the Westview Press collection, of course I will. And though it may be hard to believe, I do stick to deadlines for writing very closely.

Vol III - yes, David and I did discuss it, if a little incompletely, and I agree entirely with the idea of thematic essays. This is not least because (a) there is just too much to cover on the (20th), (b) I think there has to be some explicit acknowledgement of the way an international source got channelled into specifically national and distinct publishing traditions, and (c) for that and many other reasons, I would be very suspicious of any sense of unity in the writing of the

history of 20th comics. Trouble is, I don't think David is very interested, and it does need two 'quality assurance' hands on it, in my view. There just is too much poor scholarship around. (Incidentally, you should take a look at two recent books on comics, for just such a comparison — Roger Sabin's excellent Adult Comics: an Introduction (Penguin 1992) and Greg McCreel's scandalously bad Dark Knights (Pluto 1992).)

In connection with all the issues about Vol III, did David mention to you my idea that I've floated of a conference in about a year / 18 months of comics scholars, here in Britain, to discuss specifically: what's the state of comics research, and what priorities can we identify? It's an idea I particularly discussed with Rusty White and a few others at the Popular Culture Association conference in New Orleans in April. I sense that it might work. What do you think?

~~That's about it, I am. My honest apologies to you and for handwriting this. It's getting written at 6.45am on a holiday Saturday such is my life. We must meet sometime, in circumstances that allow talk and wine to be freely exchanged! Good luck with job-hunting.~~

Best wishes,

Mark Foster

Kunzle, June 28, 2017, Glasgow. At the Eighth International Graphic Novel and Comics Conference/Joint International Conference of Graphic Novels, Bandes Dessinées & Comics

David Kunzle admiring his copy of the American 1842 edition of Töpffer's *The Adventures of Obadiah Oldbuck* on loan to the Frank Quitely exhibition at the Kelvingrove Art Gallery and Museum. And schooling comic scholars on Töpffer and Cham. (Paul Aleixo on his left).